

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore
Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ANOOP H bearing USN 6SU20PT001 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Perfusion Technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/MsANUSREE M V bearing USN 6SU20PT002 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Perfusion Technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/MsASWATHY R bearing USN 6SU20PT003 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Perfusion Technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms AVANDHIKA P V bearing USN 6SU20PT004 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre, Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Perfusion Technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms GODSON P B bearing USN 6SU20PT005 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Perfusion Technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/MsGOPINAATH K bearing USN 6SU20PT006has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Perfusion Technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/MsMALAVIKA S bearing USN 6SU20PT007has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Perfusion Technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/MsNANDINI P bearing USN 6SU20PT008 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Perfusion Technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms SHERIN MARYAM LAL bearing USN 6SU20PT009 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre, Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Perfusion Technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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